

Appendix C: Sample Characteristics and Indicators

The data supplement includes weighted and unweighted N, weighted percentages for our overall sample, and according to demographic groupings: age, education, income, marital status, race and ethnicity, sex, gender identity, and sexual orientation.

Certain sparsely-populated demographic categories were combined to create a single larger category for analytical purposes:

- “Previously married” includes widowed, divorced, and separated
- “Hispanic (any race)” includes Cuban/ Cuban-American, Mexican/Mexican-American/Chicano, Puerto Rican, and Other Spanish/Hispanic/Latino
- “Other Non-Hispanic” includes American Indian/Alaska Native, and Native Hawaiian/Pacific Islander
- Under “Gender identity,” cisgender male is abbreviated to “male,” cisgender female is abbreviated to “female.” Transgender, nonbinary, and other gender identities are combined into a single group.

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Category	Group	N Unweighted	N Weighted	% Weighted
Overall	Full Sample	10024	10024	100.0%
Age	18-24	570	1103	11.0%
	25-34	1201	1526	15.2%
	35-44	1751	1962	19.6%
	45-54	1501	1480	14.8%
	55-64	1961	1655	16.5%
	65-74	1870	1432	14.3%
	75-84	1005	745	7.4%
	85+	165	122	1.2%
Education	Less than high school	601	922	9.2%
	High school graduate/GED	2346	2869	28.6%
	Some college/Associate's degree	2745	2640	26.3%
	Bachelor's degree	2363	1994	19.9%
	Graduate/Professional degree	1969	1599	16.0%
Income	Less than \$10,000	239	290	2.9%
	\$10,000 to \$24,999	626	693	6.9%
	\$25,000 to \$49,999	1336	1436	14.3%
	\$50,000 to \$74,999	1500	1477	14.7%
	\$75,000 to \$99,999	1266	1257	12.5%
	\$100,000 to \$149,999	2045	1935	19.3%
	\$150,000 or more	3012	2936	29.3%
Marital Status	Married	5794	5287	52.7%
	Previously married	1796	1592	15.9%
	Never married	2434	3145	31.4%
Race/ Ethnicity	Asian Non-Hispanic	448	660	6.6%
	Black Non-Hispanic	1021	1212	12.1%
	Hispanic (Any Race)	1282	1789	17.8%
	Multiracial Non-Hispanic	358	165	1.6%
	Other Non-Hispanic	66	99	1.0%
	White Non-Hispanic	6849	6099	60.8%
Gender Identity	Male	4884	4826	48.1%
	Female	5022	5062	50.5%
	Trans/Nonbinary/Other	118	136	1.4%
Sexual Orientation	Straight	8488	8367	91.1%
	Gay or Lesbian	299	280	3.1%
	Bisexual	319	363	4.0%
	Other	148	170	1.9%
	[Missing sexual orientation data]	770		

Social connection indicators below average by group

		Point Estimate Below National Average on:											
<u>Group</u>	Total number of indicators below average	Structural Indicators						Function Indicators			Quality Indicators		
		Getting Together in Person	Phone or Video Calls	Religious Service Attendance	Club or Organization Meeting Attendance	Number of Close Relationships	Number of Other Friends and Acquaintances	Interacting with People from Different Backgrounds	Getting Social and Emotional Support	Having Someone for Practical Help	Feeling Lonely*	Satisfaction with Personal Relationships	Stress from Relationships*
Asian, Black, Hispanic, multiracial, or other race/ethnicity	12	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Gay, lesbian, bisexual, or other sexual orientation	12	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Transgender, nonbinary, or other	11	X	X	X	0	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Never married	10	X	0	X	X	X	X	0	X	X	X	X	X
High School Graduate/ GED or Less Education	9	X	0	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	0	0
Household income under \$75k	9	X	0	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	0	0

*An X in the "Feeling Lonely" or "Stress from Relationships" column indicates MORE loneliness or stress than the national average